

INFLUENCE OF EDUCATION AS A WELFARE SERVICE ON PRISONERS: A STUDY ON CORRECTIONAL HOME IN WEST BENGAL

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Paper Received On: 10 July 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 25 July 2024

Published On: 01 August 2024

Abstract

We all know that prisoners are isolated apart from the mainstream of society and kept in correctional institutions for the purpose of punishing and correcting them. Prisoners also need basic things like food, drinking water, and shelter to survive like normal human beings. Prisoners get various welfare services and benefits from their correctional homes through the government. Education is one of the prison welfare services that helps prisoners change from their notorious or rude behavior to mankind and leads them back to their normal social lives. This research paper's study was conducted on a correctional home of West Bengal i.e. Asansol Sub Correctional Home. The researcher collected valuable responses from 23 samples by using both primary and secondary sources and explored prisoners' satisfaction with getting education services and its influence on them. After analyzing the respondents' data, it was found that 83% of prisoners are satisfied, and the dissatisfied prisoners are not interested in education or courses offered by the prison authority. To make prisoners interested, authorities may introduce some vocational or job-related training courses that help them find a suitable job after their release. The authority may take the initiative to introduce technological advancements in providing education services like online courses for the betterment of prisoners. This study will help the govt. in making new policies for prison welfare services and for the betterment of prisoners. Finally, it can be said that every prison authority should take the initiative to correct them by providing advanced education services and returning them to the mainstream of society.

Keywords: *Society, Welfare, Punishment, Unlawful, Prisoner, Correctional Home*

Introduction

As we all know a correctional home is a place where persons are confined to serve their punishment for any unlawful act done. As normal people need food, clothing, and shelter in their daily livelihood to live healthy, it is the same as prisoners who also need food, clothing, and restrooms to survive during their term of punishment. Prisoners get various welfare services and benefits from the correctional homes through the government. Education is one

of those prison welfare services that helps prisoners change their notorious behavior and lead them back to their normal social life. Sometimes prison authority offers some interesting story-books to prisoners for their mental refreshments. They also provide some educational training to the prisoners for their skill development. Prison authority occasionally organizes counseling programs or sessions for the prisoners to understand the present mental status of prisoners. So, it can be said that by some special educational initiatives of the prison authorities towards the prisoners that they can be changed and brought back into the mainstream of society.

Review of Literature

Davis, T. (2014), the author, explored the education service for prisoners in prison institutions in the paper. The study pointed out that providing education to prisoners was a development of welfare services in correctional settings. The paper was based on a secondary database and inquired about the evolution of education services in prison.

The author, Christian, D. (2022), stated in the article about education rights for juveniles in the juvenile justice system. The paper indicates that few states have initiated to provide the education service and different vocational for juveniles in the states. The government focused on introducing education and vocational services in juvenile schools for the well-being of juveniles.

According to the author Gawande, H. (2022), narrates in the paper about the insufficiency of education services for prisoners in India. They shall take special initiative to evaluate the existing education program and introduce new policies for better education services for the prisoners in the country.

According to the author, his research paper discussed the demolition and innovation of prison education during the pandemic situation. This paper highlighted the impact of education on prisoners. Due to a lack of technological advantage, the education of prisoners was hampered, whereas the education of the outside world was totally dependent on digital and technological systems (Bradley, A. 2021).

According to the author Pandey, U (2021), the study discusses introducing open and distance education services for prisoners in India. Open universities like IGNOU play a major role in providing free education services to prison inmates in India, which helps in prison reintegration.

According to the author Zawada, B. (2012), discussed in the study, there was a lack of service education for the prisoners. The paper's main objective was to investigate the two welfare

services for prisoners in Pretoria. The study explores the area of prison about socio-economic values and their reintegration.

According to the author, the study discussed prisoners' education and rehabilitation from this facility. He defined how education engaged and changed the minds of the prisoners and focused on the good habits of work and rehabilitation (Behan, C. 2014).

The author Vacca, J. S. (2004), discussed in the article about incarcerated people that those who have got an education and attended education-related programs are likely to return to prison after being released. Education programs help to renovate the thinking of prisoners and give focus on the positive direction in life.

Definition of Key Terms

Society- A place or area where people of different religions and different cultures live together.

Unlawful- An act which is not according to law.

Punishment- It is imposed by the court which an offender has to suffer.

Prisoner- A person who commits an unlawful act and is sentenced by the court.

Welfare- A collection of services that help people in their daily lives and shape the future of their families.

Correctional Home- An institution or home where some antisocial people are kept for their punishment.

Objective

The objective of the study was to determine the satisfaction of prisoners with education services provided by prison institutions. It also highlighted whether prisoners are aware of education services provided in correctional homes.

Methodology

The study was conducted on the prisoners of a Correctional Home of West Bengal i.e. Asansol Sub-Correctional home. Valuable responses were collected from 23 samples using both primary and secondary sources. The researcher used Excel as a data analysis tool to analyze the relevant data of respondents. This study explores the satisfaction of prisoners with education services and their health.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Valuable response regarding the respondents' satisfaction with the educational services provided by the correctional homes is interpreted. During the interview, the researcher asked

a few questions to determine whether the respondents knew about the education facilities or what education courses were available for prisoners.

Table- 1 Status on providing Educational Services to the Prisoners of Asansol Sub-CH

Name of CH	Asansol Sub-Correctional Home
Yes	19
No	4
Total	23
% of satisfaction	83
% of Non-satisfaction	17

Figure- 1 Status on providing Educational Services to the Prisoners of Asansol Sub-CH

The above graphical picture represents the prisoner’s satisfaction level with respect to educational services provided by the correctional home that 83% of prisoners are satisfied with the education service, and 17% are dissatisfied.

Findings and Suggestions

After analysis of the data of respondents of the select correctional home, it is found that 83% of prisoners are satisfied with getting educational services from the prison institution. The rest of 17% of prisoners are dissatisfied due to not interested in education or courses offered by the prison authority. It is found from various studies that there is a lack of education equipment available for prisoners. So, it is necessary to supply or make available all the necessary equipment for getting an education properly. There should also be various vocational courses for the prisoners that help them find jobs after imprisonment. Prison authorities may also improve education services by introducing technical advancements facilities like various online courses from distance universities. Authority may also take the initiative to provide some counseling or yoga sessions for the mental refreshment of the

prisoners. Prison authorities may arrange counseling sessions for prisoners, which may help to change their behavior.

Conclusion

Education plays an important role in developing human character. Good and effective education helps to create honest and candid people. This study will help the prison authority about prisoners' corrections and help them to focus on a positive way of life. This study will help prison authorities as well as govt in developing a policy on education services for prisoners. Prisoners who are interested in education get an education properly and can get help in finding jobs after their term of imprisonment. Prison authorities may also provide some job-oriented training to the prisoners, which may help them select jobs based on their own preferences. Prison authorities could take special initiative in implementing technological advancements in providing educational services like distance education or various online courses for better education of prisoners. Therefore, not only the prison authority but both the government and the prison authorities have to take the initiative and play a special role in providing better quality education to the prisoners. This study will help the government make new policies for prison welfare services and the betterment of prisoners.

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